

**Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA)
Innovative Training Networks (ITN)
H2020-MSCA-ITN-2020**

Definition of Supervisory Board

Project: 955839 — CHASS

Cu-CHA zeolite-based catalysts for the selective catalytic reduction of NO_x in exhaust diesel gas: addressing the issue of Sulfur Stability

The Supervisory Board of CHASS is composed by the one representative for each Party, as defined in the Table:

Beneficiary	Representative in the SB	Role
1 - UNITO	Prof. Gloria Berlier (F)	Coordinator, Scientific manager of WP2, Management (WP6)
2 - CHALMERS	Prof. Henrik Grönbeck (M)	Scientific manager of WP1, Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Manager (WP6)
3 - UMICORE	Dr. Anke Schuler (F)	Team member
4 - UMICORE DK	Dr. Peter N. R. Vennestrom (M)	Training manager (WP5)
ESR representative	To be appointed	